

Absolute Infinite Information Theory

(Extended ChatGPT Version)

Abstract: My theory explores the concept of information in the universe from a mathematical perspective and proposes that information is infinite, absolute, conserved, and static.

1. Information as a fundamental property of the Universe: This suggests that information is not merely a byproduct but a fundamental aspect of the cosmos, which is a viewpoint shared by some physicists and philosophers.

2. Vastness and complexity of information: I argue that the information in the universe is not only infinite but also absolute in its vastness and complexity, which is a bold assertion. The idea of absolute complexity is intriguing and could have profound implications.

3. Conservation of information: This aligns with principles in physics, particularly in contexts such as thermodynamics where information conservation is a key concept.

4. The Universe's infinity: I propose that the universe is infinite in both macroscopic and microscopic directions, which is consistent with some cosmological models but remains a topic of active debate among scientists.

5. Static nature of information: The assertion that information doesn't change or move is a bit more contentious. While certain aspects of information might be conserved, other aspects can certainly change, especially in dynamic systems.

Conclusion: My practical examples demonstrate how different sets of numbers (natural numbers, multiples of ten, multiples of hundreds) have the same cardinality (i.e., they are all countably infinite). This illustrates the concept of one-to-one correspondence, showing that each set can be put into a one-to-one correspondence with another, thus indicating they have the same "size" or amount of information, despite initial impressions that one set might be larger than another.

Can we use math to describe information in the real-world universe? Mathematics is a powerful tool for describing and understanding the universe and many aspects of reality can be modeled and understood mathematically. However, it's important to note that while mathematics can provide powerful insights, it is ultimately a human construct, and our models and theories are always subject to refinement and revision as our understanding evolves.

My theory raises thought-provoking questions about the nature of information and its role in the universe. It combines mathematical reasoning with philosophical implications, contributing to the ongoing dialogue about the fundamental nature of reality.

Note: This manuscript was written with the help of ChatGPT.

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